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Memo: A Suggestion of HRJ Typology

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A Suggestion of HRJ Typology

Based on our review of Taiwan’s state reports under the six UN human rights conventions that it has ratified or domesticated (ICCPR, ICESCR, ICERD, CEDAW, CRPD, CRC), we identify three distinct patterns of human rights justification (HRJ) in the State’s responses to allegations of rights violations, grounded in the dichotomy between State action and inaction. It should be noted that this typology does not exhaust all possible forms of HRJ; rather, we highlight these types because they help to explain when HRJs present distinctive challenges and why.

Types A and B

Briefly, when State action is criticised and the State defends that action by invoking a human rights obligation to act, we label this a Type A HRJ. When State inaction is criticised and the State defends that inaction by invoking a human rights obligation not to act, we label this a Type B HRJ.

	Defending the state action by arguing it has a HR obligation to act	Defending the state inaction by arguing it has a HR obligation not to act
Criticizing a state action	Type A HRJs	
Criticizing a state inaction		Type B HRJs

Table 1: Distinction of Types A and B HRJs by action/inaction (the author)

The main purpose of identifying Types A and B HRJs is to expose the potential conflicts between positive and negative human rights obligations that often underlie the linguistic structure of HRJs. To elaborate, a negative human rights obligation refers to the core duty to respect, whereas a positive human rights obligation refers to the core duty to protect or fulfil.

Type A HRJs typically arise when a state action allegedly violating a negative obligation to respect X right is defended by invoking a positive obligation to protect or fulfil Y right. For instance, in Taiwan’s ICCPR First Report (p. 99), concerning restrictions on migrant workers’ ability to change employers, the government argued that such limitations on migrant workers’ job mobility were necessary to safeguard nationals’ right to work and to maintain social stability. Here, the State’s action restricts the negative liberty of migrant workers but is defended as fulfilling a positive duty toward nationals. This is thus a Type A justification, where the conflict lies between competing rights-holders.

This is a familiar form of conflict in human rights and fundamental rights policymaking and judicial decision-making, where a balance must be struck between the competing interests and rights of different individuals. However, the X right (the right said to be harmed) and the Y right (the right claimed to be realised) may also belong to the same rights-holder. This occurs when the government claims to protect

or fulfil a person’s right by allegedly violating another right of that same person. We label this a paternalistic use of HRJ, as it reflects a logic of “we do this for your own good.”

For example, Taiwan once had a now-invalidated ban on female workers’ night shifts, which was criticised for infringing female workers’ right to work. The State justified this ban by invoking the need to protect female workers’ right to health and maternity. This example does not involve competing rights between different individuals. Rather, it justifies the violation of a negative obligation (the duty to respect the right to work) by invoking the fulfilment of other positive obligations (the duty to protect the right to health) owed to the same group of people. Such paternalism becomes problematic when the HRJ obscures the distinction between those who are purportedly benefited and those who are harmed.

By contrast, Type B HRJs typically arise when claimants demand that a positive duty of protection or fulfilment be undertaken, but the State responds by invoking its negative duty of respect—that is, a duty to refrain from taking action. An illustrative case appears in Taiwan’s CEDAW Third Report (pp. 77–78), where the government was questioned about the absence of comprehensive labour protections for domestic workers and the delay in adopting a Domestic Workers Protection Act. In response, the State argued that existing frameworks—such as the Employment Service Law and written employment contracts—already provided sufficient protection, and that any further measures would need to balance employers’ and employees’ freedom of contract.

In this scenario, claimants ask the government to meet its positive obligation to protect domestic workers’ rights at work, yet the government relies on a non-interventionist, negative-duty interpretation of the very same right. We therefore label this a neo-liberal use of HRJs, one that presumes State intervention itself to be the principal source of rights infringement.

The following Table 2 summarize the discussion so far:

	Defending the state action by arguing it has a positive HR obligation to protect or fulfil	Defending the state inaction by arguing it has a negative HR obligation to respect
Criticizing that a state action violates the negative duty to respect	Type A HRJs	
Criticizing that a state inaction violates the positive duty to protect or fulfil		Type B HRJs

Table 2: Types A and B HRJ by negative/positive duties

Significance of Types and B

The main reason that Types A and B is theoretically intriguing for us because conflicts between positive and negative human rights obligations complicates the determination of appropriate judicial review standards. Generally speaking, the level of judicial scrutiny varies depending on whether a case concerns the violation of positive or negative human rights obligations. Positive obligations usually trigger lower judicial scrutiny, because fulfilling them often requires policy choices and budgetary allocations. They are areas in which judges are less equipped to intervene. Courts therefore tend to defer to governmental discretion in such matters. By contrast, negative obligations require the government to “do no harm”. They are usually questions that judges are more capable of assessing. As a result, violations of negative obligations often trigger stricter judicial scrutiny. Now, when a case involves a dilemma between conflicting positive and negative obligations, it can also create conflicting standards of judicial review.

Type C

Finally, beyond Type B HRJs, a related defence that the State may deploy when facing criticism of its inaction is to argue that it has already fulfilled the relevant human rights obligation through other measures. We label this defence **Type C** HRJs.

	Defending the state action by arguing it has an obligation to act	Defending the state inaction	
		by arguing it has an obligation not to act	by arguing it has taken other actions to meet the duty to act
Criticizing a state action	Type A		
Criticizing a state inaction		Type B	Type C

Table 3: Types A, B, C by state action/inaction

Type C HRJs arise when the State acknowledges the claimed positive right and its corresponding obligation, but asserts that alternative actions have already been taken to realise that right. For example, in Taiwan’s *ICESCR Second Report (pp. 13–14)*, the government was asked whether a comprehensive anti-discrimination law exists, covering all grounds of discrimination. The government admitted that no such legislation is in place, but maintained that Taiwan has actively incorporated UN human rights conventions into domestic law, which it claims is sufficient to address all forms of discrimination. In this scenario, the government does not deny the existence of a positive duty to protect individuals from discrimination, yet it defends the absence of comprehensive equality legislation by invoking other measures—often lesser, indirect, or even irrelevant ones.

Types B and C can coexist in the same scenario, and the line between them can easily become blurred. When the State defends limited or incremental implementation of positive rights by appealing to the adequacy of existing measures, it may argue either that no further action is desirable for the sake of respecting rights (Type B), and/or that existing measures are already effective in protecting or fulfilling rights (Type C). For example, in Taiwan's initial ICESCR national report (pp. 72–77), when the reviewing committee asked, “What measures are being taken to protect foreign workers against exploitation and unfair practices?”, the State responded to concerns about excluding domestic caregivers from the Labour Standards Act by asserting that mechanisms such as an affidavit of wages and model labour contracts were already adequate safeguards. These affidavits and contracts could be interpreted either as expressions of workers' agency and their right to contract (a Type B HRJ grounded in refraining from infringing freedom of contract), or merely as administrative requirements (a Type C HRJ in which paperwork is presented as a sufficient substitute for substantive labour protections).

Significance of Type C

Unlike Types A and B, Type C does not represent a conflict between duties or rights of opposite natures. Rather, it reflects the lingering uncertainty surrounding the content and scope of positive obligations. Nevertheless, Type C responses are noteworthy and deserve recognition as a distinct category because they are pervasive, and Taiwanese NGOs report that they consume considerable time and energy. This is because the State may simply reframe existing—or even arbitrary—programmes or policies (α , γ , β , etc.) as the fulfilment of the claimed positive right. Claimants are then left with the burden of explaining why these existing measures are insufficient or irrelevant—often causing the discussion to spin its wheels endlessly. Type C HRJs thus involve a double-layered justification: the State not only justifies its failure to take the requested action (by arguing or implying that it is unnecessary), but also reframes existing α , γ , β measures as HRJs in their own right.

(Hidden) Discrimination

Not all HRJs are problematic. Many reflect genuine dilemmas and difficult policy choices that inevitably arise in a contemporary democratic society. However, HRJs become problematic when rights are used as excuses. A principled way to identify HRJs used as a pretext is to examine whether they conceal racial or sex discrimination. On the surface, such justifications may appear neutral and liberty-based, but in substance they often reproduce existing inequalities.

The discriminatory effect is evident in the paternalistic use of a Type A HRJ discussed above (where a ban on female workers' night shifts is justified as protecting women's right to work), as well as in the neo-liberal use of a Type B HRJ (where the failure to include domestic workers under labour law is justified as respecting their freedom of contract). The former restriction involves sex discrimination, while the latter exclusion involves racial discrimination. Both provide strong indications that the justifications offered are pretextual. In short, the presence of discriminatory intent and/or effect offers a powerful signal that such HRJs function as mere pretexts.

By contrast, consider an example that raises few concerns about hidden racial or sex discrimination: in Taiwan, minors are not permitted to initiate political demonstrations. The government justifies this by arguing that such restrictions serve the best interests of minors, who are deemed insufficiently mature to bear the legal responsibilities associated with the role of organiser. Although this may be paternalistic, it does not raise concerns about indirect racial or sex discrimination. This HRJ may strike an unsatisfactory balance between restriction and benefit, but it raises fewer concerns about rights being used as a mere pretext for regulation.

This leads to our final observation: if paternalistic and neo-liberal uses of HRJs are prone to harmful effects because they tend to reproduce discriminatory practices, then identifying such harmful HRJs becomes a critical task in the context of migration, where discrimination is often embedded beneath seemingly legitimate rights-based discourse.

In Sum

- Types A and B HRJs represent conflicts between the State's negative and positive obligations, which may lead to confusion about the appropriate standard of judicial scrutiny.
- Type C HRJs stem from uncertainty surrounding the content and scope of positive obligations.
- Paternalistic and neo-liberal uses of HRJs are problematic because (1) they blur the distinction between those who are benefited and those who are harmed, and (2) they may conceal discriminatory intent and/or effects.
- Such uses of HRJs frequently raise equal-protection concerns, making their identification especially urgent in the context of migration, where confronting discrimination is a critical issue.
- Collectively, these phenomena can undermine State accountability and weaken the human rights system as a whole. In this regard, HRJs, simply put, constitute a pressing accountability challenge

